

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

TURKISM AS AN IDEOLOGICAL CONCEPT IN THE LATE 19TH – EARLY 20TH CENTURY

Zhapekova G.

Eurasian National University L.N. Gumilyov, Ph.D. in History

Kushenova G.

Eurasian National University L.N. Gumilyov, Ph.D. in History

Abstract

The article analyzes the formation and development of Turkism as an ideological concept in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. It examines the intellectual origins of the movement, its influence in the Ottoman and Russian Empires, as well as its relationship with Pan-Islamism. Special attention is given to the activities of key figures of the Turkic intelligentsia, such as Ismail Gasprinsky, Yusuf Akçura, Ziya Gökalp, Akhmet Baitursynuly, and others. The study demonstrates that Turkism contributed to the awakening of national consciousness, the development of culture and education, and became an ideological foundation for national liberation movements.

Keywords: Turkism, nationalism, Ottoman Empire, Russian Empire, Jadidism, Young Turks, Alash.

Introduction

The late 19th and early 20th centuries marked a period of active national awakening among peoples residing within the boundaries of vast multiethnic empires. Against the backdrop of the decline of both the Ottoman and Russian Empires, Turkism emerged as an ideological concept seeking to consolidate the Turkic peoples on the basis of shared language, culture, and historical heritage. Within this context, Turkism formed part of a broader process of modernization and the search for new forms of collective identity, developing in parallel with Pan-Islamism.

Turkism may be understood as a system of ideas founded on the recognition of ethnic kinship and the linguistic and cultural unity of the Turkic peoples. It advocated cooperation and solidarity, the defense of freedom and independence, as well as the pursuit of progress and prosperity [1]. The relevance of this study lies in the examination of the complex historical processes that contributed to the formation of modern national identities within the Turkic world. It is essential to explore how collective self-awareness and identity were transformed into more structured, state-directed forms of national identity.

Main Part

The primary objective of this study is to analyze scholarly interpretations of Turkism in the works of both domestic and foreign researchers. A content analysis of printed publications and programmatic documents (the newspaper *Tercüman*, the writings of Yusuf Akçura, Ziya Gökalp, as well as materials of the Jadids and the Alash movement) has made it possible to trace the key concepts of Turkism and their transformation. In line with this objective, the study sets the task of examining Turkism not only as a cultural but also as a socio-political phenomenon, as well as an ideological concept, while exploring its evolution and significance in the late 19th and early 20th centuries.

The origins of Turkism lie in the intellectual debates of the late 19th century, when the process of national awakening began within the Russian and Ottoman Empires. On the one hand, Turkism drew upon traditional Islamic values, which served as the foundation

of the spiritual and cultural life of Muslim communities. On the other hand, it was significantly influenced by European ideas of nationalism, which emphasized the importance of language, history, and cultural distinctiveness as key factors in nation-building.

A central figure in the formation of Turkist ideology was Ismail Gasprinsky - an educator, publisher, and reformer who played a pivotal role in the modernization of Muslim societies within the Russian Empire. He advanced the slogan “Unity in language, thought, and action”, which became the hallmark of his program for cultural and educational revival. Gasprinsky’s vision rested on the idea that Turkic peoples, divided by political borders, could achieve unity primarily through language and education. He insisted on the creation of a common literary language, intelligible to all Turkic communities, as a means of fostering a shared national consciousness [2].

His educational reforms included the introduction of *usul-i jadid*, a new teaching method based on secular subjects and rational principles of instruction. At the same time, Gasprinsky emphasized the importance of preserving ethnic identity and cultural tradition. He opposed assimilation and the colonial policies of the Russian Empire, while simultaneously advocating for the adaptation of Western scientific and technological achievements, which made his ideas inherently modernizing.

The significance of Gasprinsky extended far beyond Crimea and the Muslim populations of Russia. His newspaper *Tercüman* circulated widely across the Russian Empire, reaching Central Asia, the Caucasus, and even the Ottoman Empire. Thus, his activities laid the groundwork for the development of Turkism as a transregional movement that united Turkic peoples within a shared intellectual and cultural space. At this stage, Turkism gradually evolved from a cultural and educational project into an ideology, which over time came to play an increasingly important political role, particularly in the context of imperial crises and the rise of national movements in the early 20th century.

An important role in the formation of Turkism was played by thinkers such as Yusuf Akçura, Ali bey Hüseyinzade, and Ziya Gökalp, who sought to unite the

Turkic peoples on the basis of shared language, culture, and religion.

Yusuf Akçura was one of the most prominent representatives of the Turkic intelligentsia at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries. His name is inseparably linked with the formation of the ideology of Turkism, as well as with the development of a concept of national identity for the Turkic peoples amid the crisis of the Ottoman and Russian Empires. Akçura received his education in the Ottoman Empire and in France, where he became acquainted with Western political thought, as well as the ideas of nationalism, liberalism, and modernization. Upon returning to his homeland, he actively engaged in debates about the future of Muslim and Turkic peoples. His worldview was shaped at the intersection of three factors: the experience of the crisis and dissolution of the Ottoman Empire; the influence of European notions of the nation-state; and the Jadid movement and broader Muslim reformist thought.

As a publicist, historian, and political figure, Akçura made a significant contribution to the development of ideas of Turkic nationalism, Islamic reformism, and modernization. His key work was the essay *Üç Tarz-ı Siyaset* (Three Types of Politics), published in Cairo in 1904. In this essay, Akçura for the first time systematically outlined his views on possible paths of development for the Turkic and Muslim peoples, identifying three main strategies: Ottomanism, Islamism, and Turkism [3]. In it, he argued that among these three — Islamism, Ottomanism, and Turkism — the most viable was Turkism, as it embodied a synthesis of national, economic, and political sovereignty [4].

Ali bey Hüseyinzade, an outstanding Azerbaijani thinker, publicist, physician, and public figure, played a key role in the formation of Turkist ideology at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries. Having received his education in St. Petersburg, he came under the influence of both European philosophical ideas and Eastern traditions, which enabled him to combine elements of Western modernization with the national and cultural revival of the Turkic peoples. One of Hüseyinzade's most important contributions was the formulation of the ideological slogan "Turkism, Islamism, and Europeanism", which reflected his vision of the three fundamental components of national development. According to his concept, Turkic peoples had to preserve their ethnic identity and Turkic language (Turkism), rely on Islamic spiritual values (Islamism), while at the same time adopting the achievements of European science, technology, and culture (Europeanism). This triad became the intellectual foundation for the further development of Turkist ideology.

In his publications, especially in the journal *Hayat* (Life) and other Azerbaijani and Ottoman newspapers, Hüseyinzade emphasized the necessity of consolidating the Turkic peoples in the face of colonial pressure and the threat of assimilation. His articles stood out for their synthesis of cultural and political analysis. Hüseyinzade actively interacted with other ideologists of Turkism, including Yusuf Akçura, Ismail Gasprinsky, and Ziya Gökalp. Unlike Akçura, who proposed three alternative paths of development (Ottomanism, Islamism, Turkism), Hüseyinzade sought to unite them into a single

harmonious system. In this way, he advanced a more comprehensive program of national revival, combining tradition and modernization.

His ideas had a significant influence on the formation of the national movement in Azerbaijan and the Ottoman Empire. Of particular importance was his impact on the Azerbaijani intelligentsia, which in the early 20th century became one of the centers of Turkist thought. After emigrating to the Ottoman Empire, he continued his journalistic and educational activity, taking an active part in shaping the ideology of the Young Turks. Hüseyinzade was an outstanding representative of Turkic ideology. His works, published in Turkey, addressed various aspects of Turkic nationalism and its impact on the development of Turkic peoples. Hüseyinzade's writings played an important role in conceptualizing the relationship between Turkic nationalism and cultural identity, as well as in laying the foundations of Turkism as an ideology aimed at the cultural revival and social strengthening of the Turkic peoples [5].

In the context of the Ottoman Empire's crisis, Turkism came to be perceived as an alternative to Ottomanism and Pan-Islamism. Ziya Gökalp developed a concept of nationalism based on Turkic identity. His works gave Turkism a clear ideological framework in which language and culture became the core of the nation. The ideas of Turkism were reflected in the activities of the Young Turks, who sought to modernize the state and strengthen it through national consolidation. In particular, Gökalp examined in detail the interrelationship between Turkic nationalism, Islam, and contemporary social processes, which constitutes an important part of the conceptual foundation of Turkic ideology. His writings also provide insight into how Turkic nationalism sought to combine traditional values with the ideas of modernization and national self-awareness [6], [7].

The activities of Akhmet Baitursynuly represented an important contribution to the development of Turkist ideas in the Kazakh milieu. The primary focus of Baitursynuly's work was the preservation and strengthening of Kazakh national identity under the colonial policies of the Russian Empire. Similar to Ismail Gasprinsky, he emphasized the crucial role of language and education as instruments of national consolidation. Baitursynuly reformed the Kazakh alphabet by creating a phonetic system based on Arabic script, which facilitated the learning process and made literacy more accessible to the wider population. He was the editor and publisher of the newspaper *Qazaq* (1913–1918), which became the leading press organ of the Kazakh intelligentsia and a key platform for articulating ideas of national revival. In his articles, Baitursynuly advocated cultural and political unity of the Turkic peoples, stressing the importance of preserving traditions while simultaneously assimilating the achievements of world civilization [8]. Within the framework of Turkism, he regarded language as the foundation of national unity; education as the means of modernization and overcoming backwardness; and self-awareness as the condition for safeguarding the independence and freedom of the people.

As the leader of the Alash party, Baitursynuly linked the Turkist idea with the practical tasks of organizing the Kazakh nation politically. His program included democratic reforms, the advancement of science and culture, and the establishment of national schools. Although the Soviet regime later accused him of “bourgeois nationalism” and “Pan-Turkism,” in reality Baitursynuly did not advocate for a utopian unification of all Turkic peoples, but rather for cultural cooperation and spiritual kinship, which he saw as vital for strengthening the Kazakh nation and securing its dignified place in the world.

The significance of Akhmet Baitursynuly lies in the fact that he became a transmitter of Turkist ideas in Central Asia, adapting them to the specific conditions of Kazakh society. His legacy continues to be regarded as a foundation of national revival and one of the key stages in the development of Kazakh statehood.

Research dedicated to Turkism opens new perspectives for further exploration of nation-building processes in the Turkic world. According to R. Zholdybalin, within Western academia the study of the Kazakh intelligentsia of the early 20th century has been focused primarily on the Alash movement [9]. Among the most notable works is that of Sabol [10], which examines the biographies and ideas of the movement’s leaders, as well as the studies of Balghamis [11] and Rottier [12], both of which analyze the formation of the Kazakh intelligentsia under the conditions of colonial oppression by the Russian Empire. D. Qudaibergenova interprets the legacy of Alash within the broader context of the national awakening of the Kazakhs [13]. Of particular significance is the work of Uli Schamiloglu [14], who advanced the revolutionary argument that Tatar intellectual thought was the first among the Turkic peoples to articulate the concept of a territorial nation—even earlier than in the Ottoman Empire, which was actively borrowing European ideas. This perspective challenges the traditional Western historiography that emphasizes exclusively the influence of Europe and Russia on the rise of Kazakh nationalism.

M. Zholseitova and M. Berkinboev [15] analyze the condition of the Turko-Muslim peoples of Russia at the turn of the 19th–20th centuries, arguing that the slowed process of modernization within the Turko-Muslim milieu was reflected in the social structure of this population, where traditionalism and religious consciousness played a significant role. This collectivist worldview, characteristic of the Muslim umma, hindered the adoption of new social and economic forms. At the same time, within Turko-Muslim society, alongside Islamic reformism, secular currents of philosophical thought were gaining ground—particularly an enlightenment-oriented movement inspired by the values of the European Enlightenment. The synthesis of these trends laid the foundation for the emergence of Turkism, which sought the creation of a national secular school, the reform of education, and the modernization of Turko-Muslim life along European lines.

Turkism also demanded from its adherents active participation in Russian political life and the formation of their own political elite. This elite consisted primarily of members of the educated strata. The ideas of the

Turko-Muslim political elite were characterized by moderate opposition to Russian authority, a stance shaped both by their social status and by the ethno-religious traditions of the peoples they represented. Turkism has often been subject to criticism. First, it is frequently employed as a tool of political propaganda. Second, the ideology of Turkism places emphasis on ethnic identity, which may lead to the exclusion of other cultures and peoples from the broader context. Third, attempts to create a unified Turkic world have repeatedly encountered real political and social barriers, rendering such ideas largely unrealistic [16].

Contemporary scholarship proposes a more flexible approach to Turkism, viewing it as a cultural and historical legacy that fosters the development of cultural ties among Turkic peoples, while recognizing and respecting diverse ethnic and cultural identities within the Turkic world.

Conclusion

At the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, Turkism became an important instrument for consolidating the Turkic intelligentsia, shaping national identity, advancing Turkic languages and literature, and ideologically preparing national liberation movements. However, it failed to achieve the project of political unification due to internal contradictions within the movement, differences in the historical experiences of the Turkic peoples, and resistance from imperial authorities. As an ideological construct, Turkism followed a trajectory from national revival to becoming an object of scholarly critique. Modern approaches suggest treating it as a cultural heritage that contributes to strengthening ties among Turkic peoples while avoiding political ideologization. It gained popularity among Turkic peoples striving for national revival and unity. Thus, in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Turkism emerged as a significant ideological current that defined the paths of national revival for the Turkic peoples. Its ideas were embodied in cultural, educational, and political initiatives and had a profound impact on the further development of national movements. Despite its limitations and internal contradictions, Turkism became an important element in the formation of modern Turkic identity and continues to remain a relevant subject in contemporary political and academic discourse.

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